

Comparing the key lexico-grammatical features of research papers and reports by ChatGPT and EFL students

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Abstract

Generative Artificial Intelligence technologies such as ChatGPT have shown great potential in facilitating better teaching and learning experiences in the EFL context. While the literature posits that ChatGPT can generate naturalistic human-like language when prompted, it remains unclear the extent to which it can simulate the lexico-grammatical choices of human writing, given real-life situational contexts. Using two corpora, ChatGPT Corpus of Academic Writing (GPT-CAW) and The Varieties of English for Specific Purposes Database (VESPA), the study draws on key feature analysis to identify and compare the pervasive lexico-grammatical features of AI-generated academic essays to student-authored ones. Statistical analyses indicate that ChatGPT relies extensively on features associated with informational density such as common nouns, pre-modifying nouns, and prepositions while EFL students focus on stance, involvement, and informational density. This suggests, that at the lexico-grammatical level, functionally interpretable linguistic differences exist between ChatGPT-generated and EFL-written academic essays. Informed by previous research, it was also confirmed that AI expresses explicit referentiality more frequently than students, although both AI and students underuse persuasion features. These findings complement previous research on the linguistic characteristics of EFL writing and present new insights into ChatGPT's lexico-grammatical choices within academic writing. The pedagogical implications of these results are also considered.

Keywords – key feature analysis; ChatGPT; register variation; artificial intelligence

1. Introduction

Recently, the research community has become interested in exploring the capabilities of the chatbot Chat Generative Pre-trained Transformer (ChatGPT). ChatGPT is a conversational chatbot that “utilizes its understanding of language patterns, semantics, and context” to actively engage its users in human-like synchronous interaction (ChatGPT -3.5, accessed March 3, 2024). From providing information for cardiopulmonary resuscitation (Ahn, 2023) and optimizing teaching materials for language acquisition (Koraishi, 2023) to collaborating with journalism and media education (Pavlik, 2023), the ability of ChatGPT to replicate human-like language is proving very useful for educational endeavors. Scholarly works have shown that ChatGPT can assume the role of a writing assistant for academic research (Imran & Almusharraf, 2023). It is also a useful tool for detecting language errors (Algaraady & Mahyoub, 2023), providing feedback (Bin-Hady et al., 2023), and improving overall teaching and learning experiences (Liu et al., 2023).

Notwithstanding these benefits, there remain challenges and potential risks posed by this conversational AI in academia, particularly in the English as a Foreign Language (hereafter, EFL) context. These include cheating and plagiarism, over-reliance on ChatGPT as a writing assistant for essays and homework, negative impacts on critical awareness and the learning process, and a decline in the originality, thinkability, and overall integrity of academic writing (see Cotton et al., 2024; Dergaa et al., 2023, Perkins, 2023, Yang & Li, 2024). Interestingly, so-called AI-generated text detectors (Kumarage et al., 2023) as well

as instructors of EFL courses (Cotton et al., 2024) cannot reliably discriminate between authentic human texts and texts generated by large language models (LLMs). Evidently, despite their confidence in verifying the authorship of narrative texts, university instructors incorrectly identified AI texts as written by Chinese L1 speakers 41.3% of the time (Wu, 2024). Consequently, when students and novice scholars rely on ChatGPT to do their work, the difficulties in learner writing are masked by the AI's (in)capability to successfully replicate human academic writing. This concern is further complicated if instructors are unable to provide feedback relevant to the needs of these students.

Bringing these issues home to the field of Applied Linguistics, Casal and Kessler (2023) observed that linguists and experienced reviewers of top journals are less than likely to correctly identify AI-generated abstracts as AI. Their study showed a cumulative accuracy rate of only 38.9% across four abstracts. For human-written abstracts, the positive identification rate was 44.1%. The authors noted that researchers who misuse AI tools can very easily fabricate data while honest researchers may be falsely accused of plagiarism. It appears that distinguishing between human-written and AI-generated content is increasingly becoming a crucial skill for decision-makers, particularly in high-stakes situations. With these issues in mind, the current study performs a linguistic analysis of AI-based EFL writing *vis-a-vis* naturalistic EFL academic writing, with the primary goal of identifying the pervasive lexico-grammatical features of both texts. Guided by previous literature, we also have the secondary goal of confirming whether explicit reference and persuasion features are characteristic of student and/or AI writing.

By conducting a comparative analysis between AI-generated and student-authored texts through corpus methods, the study makes several contributions to the field. It builds on previous literature (e.g., Ariyaratne et al., 2023; Berber Sardinha, 2024; De Cesare, 2023) in assessing the quality of texts generated by natural language processing models, particularly ChatGPT. The study also documents lexico-grammatical and similarities between texts by ChatGPT and ESL/EFL students studying linguistics in Europe. Such information has pedagogical implications, considering recent concerns about the difficulty in detecting AI-generated texts in the EFL context. Finally, the findings of this study present empirical linguistic data that may inform the training dataset of future iterations of the GPT model.

2. Literature Review

Since its public release in November 2022, the GPT n technology has earned its title as one of the most sophisticated conversational AI and natural language processing technologies of our time. This is amid various state-of-the-art LLMs such as Meta Llama, Google Gemini, and Anthropic's Claude. The current GPT -3.5 series is trained on enormous datasets representing various discourses of language usage. Some of the AI model's appealing features include high accuracy (Goar et al., 2023), versatility (Kohnke et al., 2023), and the ability to mimic human language in over 80 languages. Interacting with ChatGPT requires users to input text into the text-based interface, which then generates a response in a matter of milliseconds (see Figure 1). Users can further engage with the chatbot by providing prompts or feedback to refine a generated output. Users also have the option to use GPT -3.5, the free version of the AI model, ChatGPT Plus, which requires a monthly subscription of \$20, or ChatGPT Pro at \$200 per month.

Figure 1

The ChatGPT interface

Several studies have employed corpus approaches in analyzing the linguistic variations that exist between AI and human-written texts. Sandler et al. (2024) replicated a corpus of human conversations using the GPT-3.5 model. The actual dataset, derived from *EmpathicDialogues*, and their ChatGPT equivalents were compared based on 118 linguistic categories. It was found that human conversations are more authentic and have more variability. On the other hand, linguistic features prevalent in ChatGPT dialogues were characterized by social and prosocial behaviors, politeness, cognition, and emotion. The AI also prioritized empathy and attentional focus, and the strategic use of 1st person plural and 2nd person pronouns. Given that ChatGPT has no awareness or consciousness, it is unsurprising that it was found to be “more human than human” (Sandler et al., 2024, p.3). The chatbot generates responses purely based on pre-determined language patterns. Humans, on the other hand, often introduce personal experiences, hesitations, bias, and emotions in conversations, resulting in a less than ideal output. Thus, ChatGPT may be able to “manifest as a ‘semi-human’ living actor within human society” and memorize behaviors associated with social appropriateness but not necessarily the linguistic characteristics of conversation such as *that*-omission or the pervasive use of adverbial clauses (Al Lily et al., 2023, p. 1).

In Berber Sardinha’s (2024) article, the author assessed the quality of texts generated by ChatGPT across five dimensions of variation (Biber, 1988) in four registers: conversation, academic abstracts in applied linguistics and chemistry, L2 essay, and news. The study’s findings show that register is a strong predictor of AI’s efficacy in replicating human language. Surprisingly, across all dimensions, ChatGPT’s abilities remain quite inadequate in mimicking authentic human language in the four registers. Specifically in academic texts, AI writing was seen as more formal and informationally dense than human-authored texts. Furthermore, AI conversations were found to have less involvement features such as pronouns. According to Berber Sardinha, these conversational texts seemed scripted and pre-planned, resembling an interview or personal letter, rather than a spontaneous face-to-face conversation.

In a similar line of research, Goulart et al. (2024) compared the situational and linguistic features of essays, critiques, and personal narratives written by EFL students studying in Brazil with those generated by ChatGPT 3.5. The results, like Berber Sardinha (2024), indicate that ChatGPT produces more informational content than students. On the other hand, students’ writing contains involvement features marked in spoken interactions such as contractions, private verbs, and *that* deletion. The findings of Berber Sardinha (2024) and Goulart et al. (2024) contrast in two respects. While Berber Sardinha noted that AI expresses deficiency in the use of explicit reference in L2 essays with a mean difference of -0.4, Goulart and colleagues observe a positive mean difference of 5.16. In terms of overt expression of persuasion, Berber Sardinha found that AI lacks persuasion features in its writing while Goulart et al. observed the absence of persuasiveness in both student and AI texts.

Examining more specific linguistic features of medical content, Liao et al. (2023) observed that a higher proportion of ChatGPT writing is made up of nouns, determiners, and coordinating conjunctions, with less use of adverbs. These texts are rich in logical reasoning and writing fluency but low on informational content. The human medical texts on the other hand were more lexically diverse and provided information specific to the medical situation. Another study comparing argumentative essays of the AI to German high-school students shows that the writing of ChatGPT -3 contains more occurrences of nominalizations and clausal complexity than students (Herbold et al., 2023). Herbold et al.'s study also corroborates Liao et al.'s (2023) findings about higher lexical diversity in human-written texts ($M= 95.72$, $SD= 23.5$) than AI texts ($M=75.68$, $SD= 12.89$). Additionally, L2 student writing was relatively pervaded with modals and epistemic markers. The researchers did not find the use of discourse markers and depth of sentence complexity to be statistically significant in either of the texts, a finding observed by Mizumoto et al. (2024) but contradicted by Zindela (2023). According to Zindela, argumentative essays by ChatGPT -3 have higher lexical diversity, sophistication, and density counts than those of first-year undergraduate students.

While the literature presents somewhat conflicting findings in the comparison of linguistic features in AI- and human-written academic prose, the consensus appears to be that AI-generated essays are typically well-written compared to student-written ones. In fact, Herbold et al. (2023) conclude that “ChatGPT performs well at writing argumentative student essays and outperforms the quality of the human-written essays significantly” (p. 8).

3. Present Study

Although ChatGPT's language has been extensively studied in the last three years, scholarly works have presented inconsistent findings. One possible explanation for this could be the influence of various confounding factors that affect the outcomes of such studies. For instance, the design of prompts used to generate AI texts might significantly impact the representativeness of the output, as variations in phrasing, length, or complexity of prompts can result in different responses from the GPT model. Additionally, comparing AI-generated texts to those of expert writers, as opposed to novice learners, will inevitably yield different results due to latent variables like proficiency level. As evidenced in studies like Berber Sardinha (2024) and Goulart et al. (2024), register is a strong predictor of AI's performance, thus, we might also expect reasonable differences when exploring different registers or subregisters in a domain. Finally, LLMs like ChatGPT are continuously being retrained and updated, meaning that over a relatively short period of time, research findings may not reflect current trends. These factors highlight the difficulties of conducting reliable linguistic analyses on AI-generated language.

We attempt to address some of these limitations by building a comparable corpus of ChatGPT academic writing based on an existing corpus of EFL learner writing. Informed by the findings of previous research, the present study aims to investigate how AI-generated research papers and reports compare to student-authored ones. This is done by implementing key feature analysis, a statistical technique that allows researchers to explore the differences in lexico-grammatical features of two text samples. Consequently, the approach taken is, in part, confirmatory. Expanding on the studies discussed above, the present study asks the following research questions:

1. How does AI-generated academic writing compare to EFL academic writing in terms of 38 identified lexico-grammatical features?
2. Is explicit referentiality expressed frequently in AI or student writing?
3. Do both AI and EFL students lack persuasiveness in academic writing?

4. Methods

As we aimed to investigate the degree to which the lexico-grammatical choices of ChatGPT and EFL students differ when producing academic language, we compiled a ChatGPT Corpus of Academic Writing (GPT-CAW) based on the metadata of The Varieties of English for Specific Purposes Database (VESPA). Keyness, the degree to which a word is significantly more frequent (or infrequent) in the target corpus than the reference corpus (Bondi & Scott, 2010), was then applied to lexico-grammatical items in each corpus to extract and compare the pervasive features.

4.1. Corpora Description

4.1.1. VESPA

At present, VESPA is a 2-million-word corpus of 941 texts of EFL student assignments from three academic disciplines: Linguistics (79%), Business communication (13%), and Literature (8%). The corpus was designed with the goal “to build a large collection of disciplinary writing by L2 English university students across registers and disciplines” (Paquot et al., 2022, p. 3). The texts in the corpus are categorized into five main sub-registers, namely: critique/evaluation, proposal, report, research paper, and response paper.

In VESPA, information about each contributor including country of origin, languages spoken, university and program of study, and sex are made available. This made it possible to extract a subcorpus excluding students from an inner-circle country¹ or not in a degree-seeking Linguistics program. This was done to control for discipline and ensure that participants were L2 users of English. It may be noted that several contributors reported having more than one native language. Those with L1s that included English were also excluded from the analysis. However, minority varieties of English such as Caribbean English were retained. We further selected specific texts to ensure a representation of all the different L1 backgrounds in the corpus (see Table 1). This process left us with a dataset of 416 text samples (about 1 million words) with 39 L1 backgrounds.

The number of years that the students had been studying in English is shown in Table 2. Since the average contributor is a current undergraduate student who has 8 years of experience studying English, it was reasonably assumed that they are experienced with the English language and the academic discourse. Furthermore, all the texts in VESPA were “assignments that students submitted for course credit in disciplinary content courses” (Paquot et al., 2022, p. 5), indicating that the texts are naturalistic data of EFL writing and that the students are, at best, familiar with the writing style of the Linguistics discipline.

Table 1

L1 backgrounds represented in the VESPA subcorpus

L1 background	Corpus composition in %
Akan	0.2
Albanian	0.7
Arabic	0.2
Bosnian	0.2
Caribbean English, Papiamentu	0.5
Catalan	1.9
Catalan, Spanish	0.7
Chinese	1.2
Croatian	0.2
Danish	0.5
Dutch	5.3
Dutch, French	0.2

¹ United States, United Kingdom, Australia, Canada, New Zealand

Estonian, Swedish	0.2
Finnish, Persian, Swedish	0.2
French	21.9
French, Norwegian	0.2
French, Russian	0.2
French, Spanish	0.2
French, Swahili	0.2
German	3.6
German, Italian	0.9
Icelandic	0.5
Italian	1.9
Japanese	0.2
Korean	0.5
Latvian	0.2
Modern Greek	1.7
Norwegian	40.9
Norwegian, Swedish	0.2
Persian	0.2
Polish	1.0
Romanian	0.2
Russian	1.2
Spanish	2.4
Spanish, Swedish	0.2
Swedish	8.4
Swedish, Italian	0.2
Turkish	0.2
Vietnamese	0.5

Table 2

The education levels of students included in the VESPA subcorpus

Year of study	Discipline	Number of students	%-age
Bachelor's degree	Linguistics	288	69.2%
Master's degree	Linguistics	128	30.8%
Total		416	100%

4.1.2. GPT-CAW

The target corpus was created in 2024 using ChatGPT-3.5, which is the free version of the GPT n model. The GPT-CAW comprises 75 texts of 44,290 words and is publicly available via Open Science Framework (<https://osf.io/46kyc/>). The corpus was designed to mirror VESPA; therefore, we asked ChatGPT to role-play as a non-native speaker of English.

According to Ekin (2023), an effective prompt takes into account user intent, model understanding, domain specificity, clarity and specificity, and constraints (p. 4). Therefore, the process of computing a prompt that would yield high-quality output involved several stages. First, concise drafts were given with clear instructions to write on a linguistics research paper as an under(graduate) non-native speaker of English. However, the output had several inconsistencies with VESPA such as short text length, language

atypical of learner writing, omission of a section, and recycling topics with similar content. Prompts were refined several times to address these issues. When a desired output was reached, the format of the prompt was maintained. Although the prompt explicitly requested a word length of 1000, the AI could not produce texts longer than 785 words. The average number of words per text was 590. Furthermore, it was observed that ChatGPT consistently generated 'perfect grammar'. Students, on the other hand, make errors all the time in writing, and this was evident in the reference corpus. Since the goal was for ChatGPT to replicate EFL writing, it was also asked to produce language errors typical of English language learners.

Out of the five academic sub-registers in VESPA, only research papers and reports were included in the prompts. Overall, all the prompts met three conditions: (i) they must pertain to topics in the linguistics discipline, (ii) the texts should adhere to the genre of academic writing (e.g., abstract and result sections), and (iii) the native language background and language proficiency must be comparable to that of the VESPA contributors. One of the prompts used for the corpus compilation was:

Please write a linguistics research paper of exactly 1000 words in English on "Social media as a language learning tool: The use and effectiveness". The text should include an abstract, introduction, literature review, method, results, and conclusion sections. Be sure to add in-text citations. Your writing should look like that of a master's student in the Netherlands whose only native language is Arabic and who has been learning English for 6 years. Since a non-native English speaker may have errors in grammar, vocabulary usage, and sentence structure, make sure your writing style reflects this.

Importantly, for all 75 prompts given to the AI, the topic and L1 background were modified to reflect the VESPA subcorpus. Appendix A details the process of refining the prompt provided to the chatbot. To check the representativeness of the corpus and the validity of our findings, we followed the guidelines of domain and linguistic distribution in Egbert et al. (2022). The domain was operationalized by defining a very specific register, i.e., research papers and reports of non-native English speakers studying linguistics at the university level.

4.2. Data Analysis

Unlike other keyword approaches like keyword analysis and key part of speech analysis, Biber and Egbert's (2018) key feature analysis measures the degree to which a lexico-grammatical unit is significantly more frequent (or infrequent). The method lets researchers focus on functionally motivated lexico-grammatical features of individual texts within two (sub)corpora or varieties of texts. Over the years, key feature analysis has been used to examine text variations in online registers (Biber & Egbert 2018), statutory language (Wood, 2022), and presidential debates (Egbert & Biber, 2020), among others. Such analyses are possible as researchers calculate effect sizes for each lexico-grammatical feature and generate positive and negative Cohen's *d* values for their respective texts or corpora. This makes it possible to rank the features to determine those that are strongly associated with the corpora. Then, linguistic interpretations are provided based on the findings from the quantitative analysis (Egbert & Biber, 2023).

Using the Biber Tagger (Biber, 1988), the corpora used in the current study were annotated for lexico-grammatical and grammatical structures. 38 lexico-grammatical were selected based on their significance in previous studies of learner academic writing (e.g., Maamuujav et al., 2021; Staples & Reppen, 2016; Vo, 2019). Table 3 illustrates the 38 lexico-grammatical features included in the key feature analysis. To control for variations in text length, rates of occurrence of each feature were normed per thousand words using the Biber TagCount. The tagger is known for achieving approximately 95% accuracy (Friginal, 2018); an additional spot-check was conducted on 5% of the data to ensure the tagger's performance remained consistent across texts. The means and standard deviations were then calculated for all the features in both GPT-CAW and VESPA using R (R Core Team, 2024). Following this, effect sizes were computed to determine the largest positive (strongly associated with the target corpus) to the largest negative (strongly associated with the reference corpus) key features. Cohen's *d* values were calculated using the formula:

$$d = \frac{\text{Mean}_1 - \text{Mean}_2}{\text{Pooled Standard deviation}}$$

Where $Mean_1$ is the mean of each key feature in GPT-CAW, and $Mean_2$ is that of VESPA. we then ranked and reported the d values in standard deviation units, focusing on features with d values $\geq \pm 0.80$, which indicates a large effect size according to Cohen's (1977) guidelines. This threshold was chosen to focus only on features that demonstrate a meaningful distinction between the two types of texts.

Table 3
Lexico-grammatical features included in the key feature analysis

Nouns	Pronouns
Common nouns	Personal pronouns
Proper nouns	1st person pronoun
Pre-modifying nouns	2nd person pronoun
Post noun modifiers	It
Nominalizations	
	Clauses
Verbs	Verb + <i>that</i>
BE	complement
Existential	<i>That</i> relative clause
Modals	<i>WH</i> -relative clauses
Private	Stance <i>to</i> -complement
Passive	clause
Perfect aspect	Noun + <i>that</i> stance
Present progressive	clause
Adverbs	Others
All adverbs	Contractions
Factive	Coordinating
Non-factive	Conjunction
Attitudinal	Prepositions
Likelihood	Demonstratives
Stance	Hedges
	Discourse particles
	Type/token ratio

To address the second and third research questions, we selected and tagged the features of explicit reference and overt expression of persuasion used in Berber Sardinha (2024) and Goulart et al. (2024). Since both studies took an additive multidimensional analysis approach (Biber, 1988), they examined the same linguistic features that load on the two dimensions above. The lexico-grammatical features examined are given in Table 4. Using the normed rates of occurrence of these features, we compared their means in R.

Table 4
Linguistic characteristics of explicit reference and overt expression of persuasion

Explicit Reference	Overt expression of persuasion
<i>wh</i> relative clauses on object position	infinitives
pied-piping relative clauses	prediction modals
<i>wh</i> relative clauses on subject position	suasive verbs

phrasal coordination	conditional subordination
nominalization	necessity modals
	split auxiliaries
	possibility modals

5. Results and Discussion

The results and discussion are organized in response to the research questions of the study.

RQ1. How does AI-generated academic writing compare to EFL academic writing in terms of 38 identified lexico-grammatical features?

To investigate significant differences in the lexico-grammatical choices between AI-generated and student-written essays, a key feature analysis was performed. Only 38 lexico-grammatical features were analyzed. Each feature was first normalized, with means and standard deviations calculated. The effect size of each feature was expressed as d values by standard deviation units, to quantify the extent to which a feature is prevalent in one corpus relative to the other. The means and standard deviations are given in Table 5 with Cohen's d values presented in Figure 2. It may be noted that not all the features were normally distributed, and this may impact the conclusions we can draw from the data.

Table 5

Mean and standard deviations of the features

Linguistic feature	GPT-CAW		VESPA	
	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
Common nouns	225.8	32.12	180.7	24.87
Proper nouns	17.66	12.92	24.55	14.06
Pre-modifying nouns	72.92	29.27	23.21	10.84
Post noun modifiers	2.09	2.64	2.17	1.73
Nominalizations	154.84	52.76	66.39	19.96
Existential	7.83	4.12	9.99	4.33
Modals	7.63	4.95	15.83	7.92
Private verbs	4.31	5.20	10.14	5.19
BE	0.10	0.57	2.42	1.86
Passive	11.65	5.24	17.99	6.3
Perfect aspect	5.99	3.14	4.76	2.99
Progressive aspect	8.79	5.78	5.86	3.85
All adjectives	135.06	31.18	89.83	17.79
Attributive	110.05	23.14	57.96	14.66
Evaluative	0.10	0.43	0.98	1.16
All adverbs	14.74	6.06	38.28	9.78
Factive	0.00	0.00	1.72	1.84
Non-factive	0.12	0.46	1.01	1.09
Attitudinal	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.37
Likelihood	0.00	0.00	1.20	1.44
Stance	0.12	0.46	4.05	2.59
Verb + <i>that</i> clause	3.04	2.95	5.10	3.16
<i>That</i> relative clause	1.87	2.30	3.88	2.65

<i>WH</i> -relative clauses	0.21	1.29	0.65	0.96
Stance <i>to</i> -complement clause	5.85	2.81	5.04	2.80
Noun + <i>that</i> stance clause	0.09	0.40	1.05	1.09
Personal pronouns	8.66	9.53	25.14	12.45
1st person pronoun	3.05	11.21	7.54	9.17
2nd person pronoun	0.00	0.00	2.43	3.91
It	5.05	5.28	11.58	6.10
Coordinating	4.41	4.74	3.23	2.26
Conjunction	20.03	7.96	20.97	7.78
Prepositions	132.35	17.23	116.85	14.58
Demonstratives	0.27	1.58	4.41	2.96
Hedges	0.00	0.00	0.53	0.89
Discourse particles	0.03	0.25	0.18	0.44
Contractions	0.54	1.83	0.06	0.24
Type/token ratio	26.63	1.78	29.00	2.63

Figure 2

+/- *d* values of lexico-grammatical features

As shown in Figure 2, the analysis revealed 11 features that are key in GPT-CAW (shown as positive values) and 27 negative *d* values, corresponding to VESPA. Features with *d* values closer to zero, such as post-noun modifiers ($d = -0.04$) and conjunctions ($d = -0.12$) indicate similar rates of occurrence in the two

corpora. Although some features had large effect sizes, their normalized frequency counts were fewer than 2 (see Table 5). To avoid inflating the d values for features with too few occurrences, a minimum normed frequency threshold for features with $d \geq \pm 0.80$ was set at 10 rates of occurrences per 1000 words. Table 6 reports on the remaining 13 features that were retained for further analysis.

Table 6

Key lexico-grammatical feature with d values $\geq \pm 0.80$

Effect size	d	Feature
≥ 0.80	2.69	Attributive
	2.25	Pre-modifying nouns
	2.22	Nominalizations
	1.78	Adjectives
	1.57	Common nouns
	0.97	Prepositions
≥ -0.80	-1.05	Type/token ratio
	-1.09	Passive
	-1.12	Private verbs
	-1.14	It
	-1.24	Modals
	-1.49	Personal pronouns
	-2.89	All adverbs

The results reported above suggest that ChatGPT's writing is more informationally dense and highly descriptive compared to the writing of EFL students. This is evident by the heavy use of structural compression features such as common nouns, nouns as nominal pre-modifiers, nominalizations, and attributive adjectives. On the other hand, VESPA demonstrates a higher usage of modals and private verbs, which are generally used to convey an author's attitude or evaluation as regards a situation. Additionally, the prevalence of informality features like personal pronouns in VESPA suggests a more informal tone compared to ChatGPT. Finally, the large effect size of type/token ratio is indicative of the richness and diversity of vocabulary in students' writing relative to the chatbot.

Excerpts 1 and 2 illustrate examples from the ChatGPT Corpus of Academic Writing. In the following excerpts, the bolded texts represent the key features identified above.

[Excerpt 1]: By analyzing **instances of metaphorical usage** and tracing their **cognitive underpinnings**, this **research** elucidates how **metaphorical extension** serves as a **driving force** behind **semantic evolution**. The **findings** underscore the **dynamic nature** of **language**, shaped by **cognitive processes** and **cultural contexts**.

[Excerpt 2]: Furthermore, **community-based language revitalization programs** have emerged as **effective models for promoting language use** and **transmission within endangered language communities** (McCarty, 2011).

Crucially, all the most pervasive linguistic features of academic essays generated by ChatGPT are associated with noun phrase complexity. While academic writing has generally been characterized as relying on such nominal styles (Biber 1988, Biber & Gray 2010), it seems that the LLM is solely focused on completing the task requested by its user, with little to no interest in fulfilling other expectations of the register, such as expressing stance, possibility, etc. These results are concomitant with that of Berber Sardinha (2024) who reported that ChatGPT's academic language is rich in information-carrying features.

It also corroborates Mizumoto et al. (2024) in that AI essays have an impersonal tone and higher occurrences of nominalizations.

In excerpts 3 and 4, we demonstrate the use of personal pronouns in EFL students' writing as observed in The Varieties of English for Specific Purposes Database.

[Excerpt 3]: Throughout the next sections of this paper, **I** will talk about the definition and features of social media, and present types of social media. **I** will also discuss how social media is used a learning tool and present some papers who tackled the subject of SMLL (social media language learning). **I** will then introduce the research questions of this paper and discuss the results of a survey that **I** have conducted concerning social media as a language learning tool and its effectiveness. Lastly, **I** will put together a conclusion to sum up **my** paper, and suggest some directions that research in SMLL might take.

[Excerpt 4]: If **you** are used to netspeak because **you** have been exposed to the language used online throughout **your** life, then this kind of initialisms might not seem so strange or foreign or even new to **you**, and **you** might thus be more inclined to use them generally. Another explanation why these initialisms are not used much in the COCA might be connected to the notion of correct language, as Burrige (2004) explains. The notion of correctness when it comes to using the English language is something **you** learn at a very early age in school.

Key feature analysis of EFL student essays showed an excessive use of first and second personal pronouns. While this signals some level of informality, it also appears to serve some functional purposes. For instance, the 1st person pronoun in *excerpt 3* shows authorial presence and responsibility. The author establishes their involvement in the writing process, showing ownership of the work (i.e., *my paper*) and taking responsibility for the outcome. Previous studies (e.g., Gilquin & Paquot 2008) have shown that learners often use personal pronouns in their writing, especially when introducing new topics or ideas. This makes them 'too visible' through their writing. Similarly, Hyland (2001) found that EFL speakers of Chinese deliberately underuse "I" in essays in order to make themselves invisible. Furthermore, the second person pronoun was also used as a way of involving and engaging readers as shown in *excerpt 4*. Taken together, the use of these informality features makes students' writing rather conversational, confirming Goulart et al.'s (2024) findings.

Information packaging was also key in students' writing. However, unlike ChatGPT, it was mainly expressed using multiple adverbs:

[Excerpt 5]: One final point I would like to make is that the text itself is **quite interestingly** written.

[Excerpt 6]: Compared to the ones where they **actually** occur, they **usually** occur **more** than once.

Finally, learners often used private verbs (together with the first person pronoun) to express personal stance (see *excerpt 7*) while modals and passive voice were used to denote impersonal stance. This is also illustrated in *excerpt 8*.

[Excerpt 7]: The other analyzed types of neoclassical compounds, as well as some neologisms that *I* do not **consider** as types of neoclassical compounds, can be found in appendix 2.

[Excerpt 8]: **It was argued** that lower-class pronunciations must be avoided, those were, basically, the perceptions of correct or incorrect pronunciation.

RQ2. Is explicit referentiality expressed frequently in AI or student writing?

To obtain a single mean difference for the five explicit reference features, the average of the mean frequencies was calculated. The results, summarized in Table 7, are consistent with Goulart et al. (2024)

who found that “AI-generated texts contain features of explicit style to a greater extent than student-authored texts” (p. 14). A review of the mean scores, as presented in Figure 3, reveals systematic trends in the use of explicit reference. For example, both writers tend to use a lot of nominalizations, although AI relies heavily on them. While relatively lower in frequency, phrasal coordination was also used by ChatGPT and students. Even though these findings were also observed in the Goulart et al. study, the absence of relative clauses in student essays was not evident in our data. Excerpts 9 and 10 illustrate the differences in explicit referentiality in GPTCAW and VESPA, respectively.

[Excerpt 9]: This research **proposal**_(nn-nom) aims to investigate the **impact**_(nn-nom) of language **similarity**_(nn-nom) on the **acquisition**_(nn-nom) of grammatical gender in bilingual individuals.

[Excerpt 10]: It is not strange, perhaps, that compounding is by far the most common strategy (as many as 40% of all new words are created through compounding) (Tottie 2002), seeing as it structurally is not a very complex method, and also is efficient in the way that many new words are considered as **combinations**_(nn-nom) of two concepts, **in which case**_(wh_rel_pipe) it makes sense for such a word to be created by using the words denoting those two concepts.

Table 7

Overall mean difference of explicit reference features

Corpus	Overall mean
GPTCAW	32.2
VESPA	15.0
Mean difference	17.2

Figure 3

Differences in the mean frequencies of explicit reference features ²

² *coord_conj_phrs* = phrasal coordination, *nn_nom* = nominalization, *wh_rel_obj* = *wh* relative clauses on object position, *wh_rel_pipe* = pied-piping relative clauses, *wh_rel_subj* = *wh* relative clauses on subject position

RQ3. Do both AI and EFL students lack persuasiveness in academic writing?

The rates of occurrence for the six features that may indicate persuasion are displayed in Figure 4. The most frequent phrasal persuasion feature in both corpora is infinitives, occurring approximately 10 to 11 times per 1,000 words. The next most frequent feature in students' writing was possibility modals. In ChatGPT writing, possibility and prediction modals occurred at equal rates, each appearing more than three times per 1,000 words. Although the negative mean difference shows students exhibit more persuasiveness in their writing, the relatively low mean frequencies suggest that neither students nor AI incorporate persuasiveness in their writing. Even more interesting is the fact that when ChatGPT was asked to roleplay as an EFL student in the current study, compared to Berber Sardinha (2024) where it was not asked to roleplay, it exhibited a lack of natural persuasiveness. Given this pattern, it may be reasonably assumed that AI struggles to replicate the persuasive nature of scholarly writing. In sum, our findings are similar to both Goulart et al. (2024) and Berber Sardinha (2024). Examples of how persuasion was overtly expressed in GPTCAW and VESPA are shown in *excerpts* 11 and 12 below.

[Excerpt 11]: Moving forward, further research is **needed**_(suasive) **to explore**_(infinitive) effective strategies for language maintenance and intervention, ultimately **enhancing**_(suasive) language vitality and cultural diversity in bilingual communities.

[Excerpt 12]: Text 1, on the other hand, uses an everyday language, perhaps trying **to engage**_(infinitive) the reader with a simple and humourous tone, in taking an interest in what **might**_(mod-poss) be considered a dull, historical topic.

Table 8

Overall mean difference of persuasion features

Corpus	Overall mean
GPTCAW	3.37

VESPA	4.67
Mean difference	-1.3

Figure 4

Differences in the mean frequencies of persuasion features³

6. Conclusion

Users of ChatGPT and academic researchers across various disciplines have confirmed the ability of the AI model to generate human-like language. Nonetheless, little is known about whether ChatGPT is well-versed in approximating register-specific language. The current study aimed to build on what is currently known by exploring the distinctive features of AI-generated scholarly writing compared to student-authored ones. To this end, a key feature analysis revealed that ChatGPT relies heavily on features associated with informational density, with no persuasiveness or impressionistic features like stance ($M= 0.12$, $SD= 0.46$) and hedges ($M= 0.0$, $SD= 0.0$). The linguistic composition of ESL-EFL students on the other hand showed three main semantic categories, namely, informational density, stance, and involvement features. These results are mainly consistent with previous studies (e.g., Liao et al., 2023). Additionally, descriptive statistics confirmed Goulart et al.'s (2024) postulation that while both AI and students overtly express explicit referentiality, AI does so more frequently than students. Our study also showed that although AI lacks persuasion in its writing, this deficiency is not exclusive to AI but is also evident in student texts, as Goulart and colleagues observed.

Unlike previous studies which had the goal of determining whether AI writes better than students or vice versa, our objective was to lay the groundwork for instructors to be duly informed about those pervasive linguistic features that might help indicate whether a writing assignment could have been

³ *mod_necess* = necessity modals, *mod_poss* = possibility modals, *mod_pred* = prediction modals, *split_aux* = split auxiliaries, *sub_conj_cond* = conditional subordination, *vb_suasive* = suasive verbs

generated by AI. However, these implications should be interpreted with extreme caution. Although the boundaries of what constitutes plagiarism when consulting ChatGPT remain blurred (Okaibedi, 2023; Perera & Stomeo, 2023), it is crucial for instructors to include a clear policy on the use of generative AI tools in instructional materials. Specifically, they may wish to address the limitations and ethical implications of using ChatGPT in the classroom. For example, by knowing that the AI does not (or cannot) convey stance, hallucinates, and fabricates references (Buholayka et al., 2023; Walters & Wilder, 2023), instructors can stress to students, the importance of articulating their voice and being more critical when writing. The relationship between a lack of confidence and writing skills among ESL-EFL students is well documented. Perhaps, with proper motivation, comprehensive feedback, and encouragement, students may be determined to become better writers rather than employing AI as a writing assistant.

The study has several limitations. First, the prompts used for the GPT-CAW compilation influenced the generated output, and by implication, the results. As noted in Appendix A, prompts were revised multiple times to ensure that the output was not only comparable to VESPA but also gave ChatGPT the best chance to demonstrate its writing ability. Second, the findings were based on ChatGPT, -3.5, which is arguably less efficient than the paid ChatGPT -4 version in terms of logical composition, complexity, and diverse use of vocabulary (Herbold et al., 2023). Therefore, these findings may be specific to this version and not generalizable to the entire GPT technology. An interesting area of exploration that could not be included in this paper is the analysis of the “deliberate” errors made by the chatbot. Future studies may also wish to investigate other (spoken) registers to draw conclusions about ChatGPT’s ability to produce register-appropriate language. As we have shown, Artificial Intelligence may be able to conform to the writing conventions of academia, but it will probably never be able to mimic the thoughtfulness and depth that is required of quality human scholarly writing and research.

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Appendix A

To generate optimal results, we experimented with multiple versions of prompts before selecting the one that gave the best output.

Sample 1. I want you to write a research paper on Comparing request strategies: A case study on cross-cultural e-mail communication between three CEOs with different cultural backgrounds, with all the relevant sections including an abstract, introduction, methods, results, discussion, and conclusion. Be specific and detailed in your writing. Don't be vague or ambiguous. Ensure that your writing is representative of an undergraduate applied linguistics student who is an advanced learner of English.

Sample 2. Please write a student academic essay on Comparing request strategies: A case study on cross-cultural e-mail communication between three CEOs with different cultural backgrounds. Include abstract, introduction, literature review, method, results, and conclusion sections. Be sure to add in-text citations. Your writing should be representative of a native speaker of French who is a third-year undergraduate student at UCLouvain in Belgium and has been studying English for 4 years.

Sample 3. Please write a linguistics academic text of at least 1000 words on Comparing request strategies: A case study on cross-cultural e-mail communication between three CEOs with different cultural backgrounds. The text should include an abstract, introduction, literature review, method, results, and conclusion sections. Be sure to add in-text citations. Your writing should represent a fourth-year undergraduate student in Belgium whose only native language is French and who has been learning English for 4 years. This means that you may produce language errors. That is okay. Just ensure that your text reflects all the criteria above.

Final prompt. Please write a linguistics research paper of at least 1000 words in English on "Comparing request strategies: A case study on cross-cultural e-mail communication between three CEOs with different cultural backgrounds." The text should include an abstract, introduction, literature review, method, results, and conclusion sections. Be sure to add in-text citations. Your writing should look like that of a fourth-year undergraduate student in Sweden whose only native language is Swedish and who has been learning English for 9 years. Since a non-native English speaker may have errors in grammar, vocabulary usage, and sentence structure, make sure your writing style reflects this.